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Evaluation & Impact Assessment
ALTMERICS

<p>MAA Scenario</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Interim and <i>ex-post</i></p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Any</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>High, advanced quantitative and IT skills needed.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>Depends on the project size and data volume.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>PC and software access, data collection costs if not available.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tool # 35, 36, 37.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Purpose

Altmetrics are used to:

- Assess the performance of the projects
- Evaluate project outreach
- Assess the impact of R&I outputs.

Background and Logic

Altmetrics are metrics and qualitative data that are complementary to traditional, citation-based metrics. They can include (but are not limited to) peer reviews on Faculty of 1000, citations on Wikipedia and in public policy documents, discussions on research blogs, mainstream media coverage, bookmarks on reference managers like Mendeley, and mentions on social networks such as Twitter.

(Source: www.altmetric.com).

As alternatives to the standard scientific impact measurement, they are typically quicker to obtain and not limited to the scientific arena. Altmetrics highlight (in a visible way) the engagement (interactions) of science with practice. The numbers associated with the altmetrics should not be treated in a simplistic way, however, if we are interested in gaining the picture about impacts. They should be a starting point for the reflections over the qualities behind project dissemination, that ideally should be impacts enabling.

Altmetrics enable the measurement of attention, dissemination, influence and impact that scientific outputs have. The following examples of altmetrics can be used:

- Mentions in the news
- Mentions in blogs
- Mentions on Twitter
- Article page views
- Article downloads
- GitHub repository watchers
- Facebook shares
- Number of interactions on social media
- References in policy documents
- Commentaries from experts and practitioners.

Image source: Rahimi, Forough, et al. "How Academia and Society Pay Attention to Climate Changes: A Bibliometric and Altmetric Analysis." *Webology* 16.2 (2019).

